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***Corresponding**

Author:

L. M. Angadi
Department of Mathematics,
of Shri Siddeshwar Government
First Grade College & P.
G. Studies Centre,
Nargund, India

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Weighted residual method for the numerical solution of boundary value problems utilizing Fibonacci wavelets

L. M. Angadi

Department of Mathematics, Shri Siddeshwar Government
First Grade College & P. G. Studies Centre, Nargund,
India

ABSTRACT

The boundary value problems (BVPs) are crucial because they model real world phenomena governed by differential equations with constraints at the edges (boundaries) of a domain unlike initial value problems (IVPs) which focus on a single point. The basic idea behind wavelets is to analyze according to scale. "Wavelets" are functions used to represent data or other functions that meet specific mathematical conditions. This work proposes a numerical solution for BVPs using the weighted residual technique with Fibonacci wavelets (WRMFW). In this case Fibonacci wavelets are used as weight functions that assume basis elements which allow us to obtain the numerical solution of BVPs. Obtained numerical solutions using this method are compared with existing methods and exact solutions. There are a few BVPs to demonstrate the validity and applicability of the proposed method.

Keywords: Boundary value problems, Fibonacci wavelets, function approximation, weighted residual method

INTRODUCTION

In essence, a boundary value problem for a differential equation involves finding a solution that satisfies both the equation itself and specific conditions at its boundaries. It's important to recognize that many differential equations derived from physical models lack readily available analytical solutions. Consequently, developing numerical methods to obtain approximate solutions becomes crucial.

Differential equations can now be solved numerically using a variety of techniques. The Laguerre Wavelet-Galerkin Method [3], the Hermite wavelets method [2], the Legendre wavelet collocation method [1], and the Galerkin method employing Gegenbauer wavelets are a few examples. [4].

Wavelets are powerful mathematical tools that analyze signals, images, and data by decomposing them into different frequency components with localized time-frequency resolution. They are essential for handling non-stationary signals, allowing for efficient noise removal, data compression, and feature extraction that traditional methods like Fourier analysis often miss. Using wavelet function bases instead of other traditional piecewise polynomial trial

functions in finite element type approaches is one way to analyze differential equations. The weighted residual methods represent a broader set of approaches that encompasses Galerkin's technique. The Galerkin method is considered the most widely used in applied mathematics because of its implementation and simplicity [56].

In this paper, we developed weighted residual method using Fibonacci wavelets for the numerical solution for BVPs. This method is based on expanding the solution by Euler wavelets with unknown coefficients. The properties of Fibonacci wavelets together with the weighted residual method i.e. Galerkin method are utilized to evaluate the unknown coefficients and then a numerical solution of the BVPs is obtained.

The organization of the paper is as follows. Fibonacci wavelets and function approximation is given section 2. Section 3 deals with weighted residual method using Fibonacci wavelets (WRMFV) for the solution of BVPs. Numerical Experiment is given in section 4. Finally, conclusions of the proposed work are discussed in section 5.

FIBONACCI WAVELETS AND FUNCTION APPROXIMATION

Fibonacci Polynomials

The standard description of Fibonacci polynomials [7] is outlined as follows:

$$\tilde{F}_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & m = 0 \\ t, & m = 1 \\ t\tilde{F}_{m-1}(t) + \tilde{F}_{m-2}(t), & m > 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, these polynomials [1] can be represented in the form of powers as demonstrated:

$$\tilde{F}_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{m}{2}} \binom{m-i}{i} t^{m-2i}, \quad m > 0 \quad (2)$$

Also, if $\tilde{F}_m(t)$, $m = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$ are Fibonacci polynomials, then

$$\int_0^1 \tilde{F}_m(t) \tilde{F}_n(t) dt = \sum_{i=0}^{\frac{m}{2}} \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{n}{2}} \binom{m-i}{i} \binom{n-j}{j} \left(\frac{1}{m+n-2i-2j+1} \right) \quad (3)$$

Fibonacci wavelets:

Fibonacci wavelets [6-7] are defined in the following manner:

$$\psi_{n,m}(t) = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \frac{\hat{F}_m(2^{k-1}t - n)}{\sqrt{W_m}}, & \frac{n}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{n+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In which $\hat{F}_m(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{W_m}} \tilde{F}_m(t)$ with $W_m(t) = \int_0^1 \{\tilde{F}_m(t)\}^2 dx$

where W_m , for $m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M - 1$ are obtained by equation (3), and m denotes the order of the Fibonacci polynomials and $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$, $k \in N$.

For instance, for $k = 1$ and $M = 3$, the Fibonacci wavelet bases as given below:

$$\psi_{1,0}(t) = 1, \quad \psi_{1,1}(t) = \sqrt{3}t, \quad \psi_{1,2}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{15}{28}}(1 + t^2) \text{ and so on.}$$

Function Approximation

Let us consider $y(t) \in L^2(0, 1]$ that can be represented through Fibonacci wavelets in the subsequent way:

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} c_{n,m} \psi_{n,m}(t) \quad (5)$$

By truncating the infinite series referenced earlier, we have

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{2^{k-1}} \sum_{m=0}^M c_{n,m} \psi_{n,m}(t) \quad (6)$$

Convergence of Fibonacci wavelets

Theorem: If a continuous function $y(t) \in L^2(R)$ defined on $[0, 1)$ be bounded, i.e. $y(t) \leq K$, then the Fibonacci wavelets expansion of $y(t)$ converges uniformly to it [8].

METHOD OF SOLUTION

Consider the boundary value of the problem is of the form,

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} + P(t) \frac{dy}{dt} + Q(t) y = f(t) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{With boundary conditions } y(0) = \alpha, \quad y(1) = \beta \quad (8)$$

Where $P(t)$, $Q(t)$, $f(t)$ be a continuous functions of t or constants and α , β are constants.

$$\text{Write the Eq. (7) as } R(t) = \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} + P(t) \frac{dy}{dt} + Q(t) y - f(t) \quad (9)$$

where $R(t)$ is the residual of the Eq. (7). When $R(t) = 0$ for the exact solution and $y(t)$ will satisfy the boundary conditions.

Consider the trail series solution of the Eq. (7), $y(t)$ defined over $[0, 1)$ can be expanded as a modified Fibonacci wavelets, satisfying the given boundary conditions which is involving unknown parameter as follows,

$$y(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{2^{k-1}} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} c_{n,m} \psi_{n,m}(t) \quad (10)$$

where $c_{n,m}$'s are unknown coefficients to be determined.

Accuracy in the solution is increased by choosing higher degree Fibonacci wavelet polynomials.

Differentiating Eq. (10) twice with respect to t and substitute the values of in y , $\frac{dy}{dt}$, $\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2}$

To find $c_{n,m}$'s we choose weight functions as assumed bases elements and integrate on boundary values together with the residual to zero [9].

$$\text{i.e. } \int_0^1 \psi_{1,m}(t) R(t) dt = 0, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

then we obtain a system of linear algebraic equations, on solving this system, we get unknown parameters. Then substitute these unknowns in the trail solution i.e. Eq. (3.4), we obtained numerical solution of Eq. (7).

In order to know the accuracy of WRMFV for the test problems, we use the error measure i.e. maximum absolute error. The maximum absolute error will be calculated by

$$E_{\max} = \max |y(t)_e - y(t)_a|,$$

where $y(t)_e$ and $y(t)_a$ are exact and approximate solutions respectively.

Numerical Experiment

Problem 1 First, consider the boundary value problem [10],

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} - 4y = 4 \cosh(1), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1 \tag{11}$$

With boundary conditions: $y(0) = 0, \quad y(1) = 0$ (12)

The implementation of the Eq. (11) as per the method explained in section 3 is as follows: and its residual can be written as:

$$R(x) = \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} - 4y - 4 \cosh(1) \tag{13}$$

Now, choosing the weight function $w(t) = t(1-t)$ for Euler wavelet bases to satisfy the given boundary conditions Eq. (4.2), i.e. $\psi(t) = w(t) \times \varphi(t)$

$$\psi_{1,0}(t) = \varphi_{1,0}(t) \times t(1-t) = t(1-t)$$

$$\psi_{1,1}(t) = \varphi_{1,1}(t) \times t(1-t) = (\sqrt{3}t)t(1-t)$$

$$\psi_{1,2}(t) = \varphi_{1,2}(t) \times t(1-t) = \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{15}{28}}(1+t^2) \right\} t(1-t)$$

Assuming the trial solution of Eq. (4.1) for $k = 1$ and $M = 3$ is given by

$$y(t) = c_{1,0} \psi_{1,0}(t) + c_{1,1} \psi_{1,1}(t) + c_{1,2} \psi_{1,2}(t) \tag{14}$$

Then the Eq. (14) becomes

$$y(t) = c_{1,0} \{t(1-t)\} + c_{1,1} \{(\sqrt{3}t)t(1-t)\} + c_{1,2} \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{15}{28}}(1+t^2)t(1-t) \right\}$$

$$\Rightarrow y(t) = c_{1,0}(t-t^2) + c_{1,1}\sqrt{3}(t^2-t^3) + c_{1,2}\sqrt{\frac{15}{28}}(t-t^2+t^3-t^4) \tag{15}$$

Differentiating Eq. (15) twice w.r.t. t and substitute the values of $y, \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2}$ in

Eq. (13), to get the residual of Eq. (11). The “weight functions” are the same as the basis functions.

Then by the weighted Galerkin method, consider the following:

$$\int_0^1 \psi_{1,j}(t) R(t) dt = 0, \quad j = 0, 1, 2 \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{For } j = 0, 1, 2 \text{ in Eq. (16),} \\
 \text{i.e. } \left. \begin{array}{l} \int_0^1 \psi_{1,0}(t) R(t) dt = 0 \\ \int_0^1 \psi_{1,1}(t) R(t) dt = 0 \\ \int_0^1 \psi_{1,2}(t) R(t) dt = 0 \end{array} \right\} \quad (17)
 \end{array}$$

From Eq. (17), we have system of algebraic equations with unknown coefficients i.e. $c_{1,0}$, $c_{1,1}$ and $c_{1,2}$.

Solving this by Gauss elimination method, we obtain the values for $c_{1,0} = -1.6347$, $c_{1,1} = 0.4123$ and $c_{1,2} = -0.9770$. Substituting these values in Eq. (4.5), we get the numerical solution.

The comparison of numerical solution and the absolute errors are presented in Table 1 and numerical solution with exact solution of Eq. (4.1) is $y(t) = \cosh(2t - 1) - \cosh(1)$ in Figure 1.

Table 1: Comparison of numerical solution and absolute error with exact solution of the problem 4.1.

t	Numerical solution		Exact solution	Absolute error	
	FDM	WRMFW		FDM	WRMFW
0.1	-0.20513451	0.2056976	-0.2056457	5.11e-04	5.19e-05
0.2	-0.35675116	-0.3576911	-0.3576124	8.61e-04	7.87e-05
0.3	-0.46091565	-0.4619814	-0.4620083	1.09e-03	2.69e-05
0.4	-0.52179149	-0.5228533	-0.5230139	1.22e-03	1.61e-04
0.5	-0.54181677	-0.5428753	-0.5430806	1.26e-03	2.05e-04
0.6	-0.52179149	-0.5228997	-0.5230139	1.22e-03	1.14e-04
0.7	-0.46091465	-0.4620626	-0.4620083	1.09e-03	5.43e-05
0.8	0.356751167	-0.3577839	-0.3576124	8.61e-04	1.72e-04
0.9	-0.20513451	-0.2057672	-0.2056457	5.11e-04	1.22e-04

Fig. 1: Comparison of numerical solution with exact solution of the problem 1.

Problem 2 Next, consider the singular boundary value problem [3],

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} - \frac{dy}{dt} = -1, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1 \tag{18}$$

With boundary conditions: $y(0) = 0, \quad y(1) = 0$ (19)

As explained in section 3 and in the previous problem, we obtain the values of $c_{1,0} = 0.3737, c_{1,1} = 0.0664$ and $c_{1,2} = 0.0640$. Substituting these values in Eq. (4.5), we get the numerical solution. The comparison of numerical solution and the absolute errors are presented in Table 2 and numerical solution with exact solution of Eq. (4.8) is

$$y(t) = t - \left(\frac{e^t - 1}{e - 1} \right) \text{ in Figure 2.}$$

Table 2: Comparison of numerical solution and absolute error with exact solution of the problem 2.

t	Numerical solution			Exact solution	Absolute error		
	FDM	Ref[11]	WRMFW		FDM	Ref[11]	WRMFW
0.1	0.310289	0.038684	0.038826	0.038793	1.27e-03	1.09e-04	3.30e-05
0.2	0.590204	0.071009	0.071167	0.071149	1.43e-03	5.00e-05	1.80e-05
0.3	0.812347	0.096232	0.096445	0.096390	3.33e-03	1.58e-04	5.50e-05
0.4	0.954971	0.113656	0.113770	0.113769	3.92e-03	1.13e-04	1.00e-06
0.5	1.004126	0.122420	0.122440	0.122459	4.13e-03	3.90e-05	1.90e-05
0.6	0.954971	0.121367	0.121539	0.121546	3.92e-03	1.79e-04	7.00e-06
0.7	0.812347	0.109825	0.110025	0.110020	3.33e-03	1.95e-04	5.00e-06
0.8	0.590204	0.086853	0.086805	0.086764	2.42e-03	8.90e-05	4.10e-05
0.9	0.310289	0.050414	0.050580	0.050545	1.27e-03	1.31e-04	3.50e-05

Fig. 2: Comparison of numerical solution with exact solution of the problem 2.

Problem 3 Next, consider another boundary value problem [12],

$$\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} - y = t - 1, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1 \quad (20)$$

With boundary conditions: $y(0) = 0, \quad y(1) = 0 \quad (21)$

As per section 3, the values of the unknown coefficients i.e. $c_{1,0} = 0.2842$, $c_{1,1} = -0.1114$ and $c_{1,2} = 0.0414$. To obtained of Eq. (20), substitute these values of $c_{1,0}$, $c_{1,1}$ and $c_{1,2}$ in Eq. (4.5).

A comparison of the numerical solution to the absolute errors in Table 3 as well as Figure 3 shows the numerical solution to the exact solution of Eq. (20)

$$y(t) = -\left(\frac{1}{1 - e^2}\right)e^t + \left(\frac{e^2}{1 - e^2}\right)e^{-t} - t + 1$$

Table 3: Comparison of numerical solutions and absolute error with the exact solution for test problem 3.

t	Numerical solution		Exact solution	Absolute error	
	Ref[12]	WRMFW		Ref[12]	WRMFW
0.1	0.0276352	0.0265959	0.0265183	1.12e-03	7.76e-05
0.2	0.0453501	0.0443398	0.0442945	1.06e-03	4.53e-05
0.3	0.0545619	0.0544622	0.0545074	5.50e-05	4.52e-05
0.4	0.0566876	0.0581207	0.0582599	1.57e-03	1.39e-04
0.5	0.0531447	0.0564005	0.0565906	3.45e-03	1.90e-04
0.6	0.0453501	0.0503136	0.0504834	5.13e-03	1.70e-04
0.7	0.0347212	0.0407997	0.0408782	6.16e-03	7.85e-05
0.8	0.0226751	0.0287255	0.0286795	6.00e-03	4.60e-05
0.9	0.0106289	0.0148852	0.0147663	4.14e-03	1.19e-04

Fig. 3: Comparison of numerical solution with exact solution of the problem 3.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, proposed the WRMFW for the numerical solution of boundary value problems. Form the above tables and figures; it is observed that, the numerical solutions obtained by the proposed method are better than the existing methods (FDM, Ref [11] & Ref [12]) and nearer to the

exact solution. Also, the absolute error from this method is very less as compared with the existing methods (FDM, Ref [11] & Ref [12]).

Hence the WRMFW is very effective for solving boundary value problems.

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